

Search for new physics with long-lived and unconventional signatures in CMS

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Abstract

A selection of new results from the CMS detector is presented. These results focus on searches for long lived particles (LLPs) and were produced with Run 2 data. In addition, new trigger algorithms targeting the decays of LLPs are presented. These trigger algorithms are currently in use during Run 3.

1 Introduction

The CMS experiment concluded data taking for Run 2 in 2018 [1]. The full Run 2 data set comprises the data that was collected during 2016, 2017, and 2018. There have been many new results since the conclusion of data acquisition for Run 2. This report will focus on three new results from CMS, searching for decays to long lived particles (LLPs). Following these new results, this report will describe some new trigger strategies being employed for the Run 3 data taking period, which aim to improve the CMS detector's sensitivity to decays of LLPs. Two of these results will focus on searches for long lived heavy neutral leptons (HNLs) and again two of these searches will employ a novel technique of searching for LLPs based on the presence of the muon detector showers (MDSs) signature.

2 New Physics Results

2.1 Search for long lived HNLs using a deep neural net tagger

This search employs a novel deep neural network (DNN) tagger to identify the displaced jets decaying from the HNL [2]. The DNN input features consist of both global jet and jet constituent information. Global jet information used includes p_T , $|\eta|$, jet mass, jet area, and the fraction of energy deposited by the constituents into the electromagnetic of hadronic calorimeters. The jet constituents are grouped into the following categories, charged particle flow (PF) candidates [3], neutral PF candidates, secondary vertices, and PF electrons and muons. Events are selected based on the presence jets and two leptons (electrons or muons).

The search probes a large range of HNL mass and lifetimes. Results are interpreted in terms of the coupling strength $V_{\ell N}$ for a given lepton ℓ and the HNL mass. No excess is found with respect to the standard model background. Figure 2.1 displays the limits on the absolute value of the coupling strength $|V_{\ell N}|^2$ as a function of HNL mass m_N for $\ell = e, \mu, \tau$ and various coupling scenarios.

Figure 1: Limits on the lepton coupling strength to HNLs, $|V_{\ell N}|^2$ as a function of HNL mass m_N . Multiple coupling scenarios are shown, for each scenario, the limit was computed with the HNL coupling to a particular lepton ℓ either turned on (1) or off (0) [2].

2.2 Search for LLPs decaying in the CMS muon detectors

This search employs a new technique to search for decays to LLPs in the CMS muon detector system [4]. Here, the muon detector is used as calorimeter to detect the shower produced by the decay of particles interacting with the steel between the calorimeters and the muon system. The search selects events based on a large cut on the the missing transverse momentum (MET). Showers may be formed in either the barrel or endcap region of the detector. For signal, the cluster size is large, containing a large number of reconstructed hits in the muon system, while this is not true for the expected background. Figure 2.2 shows distributions of the cluster size for the background and for various signal samples. The background shown here corresponds to data taken from events not consistent with the bunch crossing that produces the primary vertex.

Figure 2: Cluster size (given by the number of reconstructed hits N_{hits}) distribution for clusters formed by data and multiple signal points of varying LLP mass [4].

The results are interpreted in terms of the Twin Higgs model [5, 6]. No excess with respect to the standard model background was observed. Limits were produced on the branching fraction of Higgs decays to LLPs $BR(H \rightarrow SS)$ as a function of the LLP mass and mean decay length ($c\tau$). Further, decays of the LLP to pairs of d quarks, τ leptons, and pairs of pions are considered separately. Figure 2.2 shows the limits on $BR(H \rightarrow SS)$ for the three scenarios described above. This signature is sensitive to a wide range of LLP mass, results here range from 0.4 to 55 GeV.

Figure 3: Upper limits on the branching fraction of the Higgs boson to two long lived scalar particles S as a function of the LLP mean decay length. The left plot displays the scenario when the LLP decays to a pair of d quarks, the center displays the scenario when the LLP decays to a pair of neutral pions, and the right plot displays the scenario when the LLP decays to a pair of τ leptons [4].

2.3 Search for long-lived HNLs decaying in the CMS muon detectors

This search is again a search for long lived HNLs, however this search utilizes the same muon detector shower (MDS) signature as described in the previous section [7]. The MDS signature can be produced by either hadronic or electromagnetic showers, thus making it a viable option to search for long lived HNLs decaying in the muon system. Events are selected by the presence of a single lepton and then signal events are distinguished from background events based on the size of the cluster in the muon system, again high multiplicity reconstructed hits is consistent with the signal model.

Results are interpreted in terms of the lepton coupling strength $V_{\ell N}$ to the HNL N , where ℓ can be either an electron, muon, or tauon. No excess was seen with respect to the standard model background. Upper limits on the lepton coupling strength are produced as a function of the HNL mass m_N . Figure 2.3 displays the upper limits on the lepton coupling strength parameter as a function of the HNL mass in all three analysis channels, the electron, muon, and tauon channel.

Figure 4: Upper limits on the lepton coupling strength parameter as a function of HNL mass. The leftmost/center/rightmost plot displays the results in the electron/muon/tauon channel [7].

3 New LLP aware triggers

To increase the sensitivity of the CMS detector to LLPs, new triggers must be developed that are capable of selecting events which may contain these objects. In Run 2 there were a very limited number of these LLP aware triggers available and many analyses resorted to the use of high MET and associated production based triggers to select events for analysis. At CMS, a two tier trigger system is used. Events are first filtered by a hardware based trigger known as level-1 (L1). Events are then further processed by software based triggers known as the high level trigger (HLT).

During the long shutdown between Run 2 and Run 3, a new L1 trigger was constructed which reconstructs and identifies candidate clusters in the CMS muon detector [8, 9]. This new L1 trigger specifically works on identifying potential clusters formed in the endcap region of the CMS muon detector. Figure 3 shows the efficiency of this new L1 trigger as a function of the largest size cluster for a given event. One can see that this trigger is highly efficient for large clusters, which, as shown above, are the types of clusters most consistent with LLP signal models. New results utilizing this trigger will be available with the release of Run 3 searches for LLPs.

Figure 5: L1 trigger efficiency as a function of the largest size cluster in an event [8].

4 Conclusion

The CMS experiment remains committed to the search for new physics. Run 2 saw an increase in the search for new physics containing LLPs. Encouraging results were produced using novel methods to search for this unusual signature. In this report, results were made utilizing novel ML based methods to identify LLPs. This report also described the unconventional use of the CMS muon detector to search for LLP decays which produce hadronic and electromagnetic showers in the muon system. Run 3 presents a new opportunity to use the experience gained from these Run 2 searches to push the boundaries for new physics at CMS, one way this may be done is with the new LLP aware triggers which may aid in the selection of candidate events containing LLP decays for study.

References

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